

Review

Towards a standardised monitoring of ecosystem condition: A literature review on indicators and their data sources

Isabel Nicholson Thomas^{a,*}, Filipe Bernardo^{b,c,d}, Constantin Cazacu^e, Ján Černecký^f, Chiara Cortinovis^g, Bálint Czúcz^h, Helena Duchkova^{i,j}, Martina Kičić^k, Sabine Lange^l, Xavier Lecomte^m, Zhi Yi Vanessa Limⁿ, Alon Lotan^o, Ulla Mörtberg^p, Chiara Parretta^g, Paula Rendón^q, Philip Roche^m, Eszter Tanács^r, Dijana Vuletić^k, Christos Zoumides^s, Adrienne Grêt-Regamey^a

^a Planning of Landscape and Urban Systems, Institute for Spatial and Landscape Development, ETH Zürich, Stefano-Franscini-Platz 5, 8093 Zürich, Switzerland

^b Fundação Gaspar Frutuoso, University of the Azores, Rua da Mãe de Deus 9500-321 Ponta Delgada, Portugal

^c Faculty of Sciences and Technology, University of the Azores, 9501-801 Ponta Delgada, Portugal

^d IVAR, Institute of Volcanology and Risks Assessment, University of the Azores, 9501-801 Ponta Delgada, Portugal

^e University of Bucharest, Splaiul Independenței 91-95, București, CP 050095, Romania

^f Institute of Landscape Ecology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Akademická 2, 949 01 Nitra, Slovakia

^g Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, via Mesiano 77, 38123 Trento, Italy

^h Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, P.O. Box 5685 Torgarden, NO-7485 Trondheim, Norway

ⁱ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělá 986/4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic

^j Faculty of Humanities, Charles University in Prague, Pátkova 2137/5, 182 00 Praha 8, Czech Republic

^k Croatian Forest Research Institute, Cvjetno naselje 41, HR-10450 Jastrebarsko, Croatia

^l Leibniz University Hannover, Institute of Earth System Sciences, Physical Geography and Landscape Ecology, Schneiderberg 50, 30167 Hannover, Germany

^m Aix-Marseille Univ, INRAE, UMR RECOVER, 3275 Route de Cézanne, 13182 Aix-en-Provence cedex 05, France

ⁿ Institute of Science, Technology and Policy, ETH Zürich, Universitätsstrasse 41, 8092 Zürich, Switzerland

^o The Kadas Green Roofs Ecology Research Center, Institute of Evolution, University of Haifa, Mt. Carmel, Haifa 3498838, Israel

^p Dept. of Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, SE-10044 Stockholm, Sweden

^q King Juan Carlos University, Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, 28933 Madrid, Spain

^r HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Institute of Ecology and Botany, H-2163 Vácraátót, Alkotmány utca 2-4., Hungary

^s Energy, Environment and Water Research Center (EEWRC), The Cyprus Institute, PO Box 27456, Nicosia 1645, Cyprus

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ecosystem condition

Review

Spatially explicit

Indicators

ABSTRACT

Easily updatable information on ecosystem condition (EC) is essential for understanding trends in ecosystem degradation and prioritising restoration efforts. However, assessing the state, health, or quality of ecosystems is a complex and multidisciplinary challenge, resulting in a wide array of approaches documented in the scientific literature. With growing emphasis on international restoration targets and discussion on how to effectively address EC within established accounting frameworks, the need for robust, systematic methods for assessing EC is increasingly evident. This study reviews recent applications of spatially explicit indicators for mapping EC, with the aim of highlighting the main indicators used in research and related data sources. We find that certain ecosystem types, such as forests, are assessed more frequently, and that most indicators employed reflect structural attributes of ecosystems. Compositional and functional characteristics remain comparatively under-explored. We show that the data used to develop metrics vary across ecosystem types, but remote sensing is widely used to develop spatially explicit and continuous indicators. Our results provide valuable insights on the challenge of comprehensive and systematic assessment of EC, and can stimulate discussion on potential minimum sets of indicators for EC. We highlight future directions for research in this field which would allow for a more complete and robustly informed use of indicators, supported by well-established data-to-indicator pipelines.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: inthomas@ethz.ch (I. Nicholson Thomas).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113952>

Received 1 April 2025; Received in revised form 25 July 2025; Accepted 25 July 2025

Available online 11 August 2025

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1. Introduction

The potential of biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration to address both the global climate crisis and biodiversity loss is increasingly recognised (Leclère et al., 2020; Seddon et al., 2020), with urgent calls for transformative change to halt widespread degradation of ecosystems and the decline in nature's contributions to human well-being (Díaz et al., 2018). Reflecting this urgency, the United Nations declared 2021–2030 as the 'Decade on Restoration', indicating the urgent need for coordinated efforts. The adoption of key international policy frameworks, including the European Union (EU)'s biodiversity strategy for 2030 in 2020, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) in 2022 and the EU's Regulation on nature restoration in 2024, have established ambitious long-term targets for ecosystem restoration extending to 2050. Achieving these goals requires robust and meaningful sets of indicators to track progress and guide necessary action (Nicholson et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2013). Previous efforts to achieve ambitious ecological goals have highlighted the need to ensure that, in addition to being credible, salient and legitimate, such indicators are practical in terms of feasibly providing information across relevant spatial and temporal scales (Butchart et al., 2016; Van Oudenhoven et al., 2018).

In this context, recent research efforts have focused on improving the systematic assessment of ecosystem condition (EC). EC is defined as the "quality of an ecosystem measured in terms of its abiotic and biotic characteristics" (United Nations et al., 2024). The assessment and monitoring of EC is essential to promptly identify those degraded ecosystems in need of restoration (Navarro et al., 2017). To plan and evaluate conservation and restoration measures, spatially continuous information on EC with the adequate resolution to capture relevant ecological features and their changes at ecosystem-specific scales is needed (Domisch et al., 2019). Such information plays a crucial role in ensuring that planners, especially those less familiar with the concept of EC, can engage with these concepts at scales relevant to integrated planning frameworks (Tulloch et al., 2021). The concept of EC is also important for the requirements defined in the EU Habitats Directive (HD), Birds Directive (BD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD), where Member States are required to assess the conservation status of selected habitats and species as well as ecological status or potential for water bodies (art. 17 HD (European Commission, 1992), art. 12 BD (European Commission, 2007), art. 15 WFD (European Commission, 2000)). Furthermore, EC is directly related to human well-being through determining the provisioning of ecosystem services (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment et al., 2018). Thus, integrating EC information strengthens ecosystem services assessments, thereby increasing their relevance and encouraging their uptake by decision-makers (Barton et al., 2024). A key requirement for such integration is the use of continuous spatially explicit information which enables ecosystem services mapping at adequate resolution and effective comparison of EC at different locations in a scientifically robust and transparent way (Vallecillo et al., 2022).

Consistently and accurately mapping EC presents several challenges. Firstly, there is inherent difficulty in developing approaches that can be universally applied across different ecosystem types with distinct management needs, while remaining easily interpretable across diverse fields in the ecological and environmental sciences (Smit et al., 2021). Various overlapping concepts, *inter alia* ecosystem integrity, state, health, and function, are employed to describe ecosystems, each reflecting a different underlying perspective on nature and its integrity (Roche & Campagne, 2017). Previous research has highlighted that this diversity of definitions is reflected in a large variety of methods employed to assess EC (Rendon et al., 2019). Secondly, data limitations often restrict the production of spatially explicit EC estimates (Rendon et al., 2019). The selection of indicators for assessment is therefore often driven by data availability, which is prioritized over thematic relevance (Maes et al., 2020). Previous reviews summarising the approaches used

for measuring EC in marine ecosystems (Smit et al., 2021) and in grasslands and forests (Soubray et al., 2021) have further underlined the need for a strategic approach to the selection of indicators and their underlying datasets.

The System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework (United Nations et al., 2024), of which EC is one of five core accounts, represents the main international effort to date towards standardising EC indicators. While the SEEA-EA framework is focused on ecosystem accounting, i.e. the systematic measurement and reporting on stocks and flows of natural capital, these advancements are also applicable to broader ecosystem assessment efforts, supporting the evaluation of EC for wider purposes. A key development in this regard is the Ecosystem Condition Typology (ECT) proposed by Czúcz et al. (2021). This hierarchical classification system organises indicators into abiotic, biotic, and landscape characteristics. Building on this, Vallecillo et al. (2022) suggested ecosystem-specific indicators and data sources for EU reporting. However, ensuring consistent indicator application across contexts remains a critical challenge, highlighting the need for transferable and updatable indicators that can support scalable monitoring efforts (Rendon et al., 2019).

This study aims to support the standardisation efforts essential for EC monitoring by identifying key spatially explicit indicators and datasets used to assess ecosystem condition. Through a comprehensive review of recent literature, we examine the completeness of spatial data applications in capturing essential ecosystem characteristics and identify the main indicators and their associated datasets. We provide an overview of general patterns in the application of EC indicators in the literature and present the key types of datasets associated with the most frequently applied indicators. We discuss these findings in relation to the development of context-sensitive yet comparable indicator sets that balance standardisation with ecological relevance for ecosystem condition assessment. Our review responds to two main research questions:

- (i) what is the state of the art of spatially explicit EC assessment in the scientific literature?
- (ii) what are the main indicators being applied for the assessment of EC in different ecosystem types, and what types of data are used for their development?

2. Material and methods

2.1. Key working concepts

The review focused on scientific articles in which indicators were applied in the spatially explicit assessment of EC. For our analysis, we defined spatially explicit assessments as having continuous coverage across the area studied and being specified at the level of basic spatial units (i.e. grid cells or pixels), small ecosystem assets, or accounting areas. Throughout the review, we accepted a variety of different synonyms and related concepts as being equivalent to EC, including ecosystem and ecological *state, health, integrity, quality, and function*. In the context of ecosystem accounting, the term "indicator" refers to a version of an ecosystem condition variable which has been rescaled in comparison to a certain reference level, such as a historical baseline or a pristine ecosystem state. In this review we applied the term broadly to include both rescaled and non-rescaled variables. For instance, chlorophyll-a concentration, an indicator of the chemical composition of freshwater ecosystems, could be presented as a rescaled indicator of values from low to high when compared to an established reference level, or simply as an absolute concentration value (non-rescaled) to convey ecosystem condition.

For analysis, we grouped indicators according to the ECT, which provides a hierarchical classification of indicators in which the abiotic, biotic and landscape characteristics of an ecosystem are further subdivided into 6 indicator classes. The full details of these classes (physical state characteristics, chemical state characteristics, compositional state

characteristics, structural state characteristics, functional state characteristics, and landscape and seascape characteristics), are included in Table A1. It should be noted that a significant number of the indicators applied in the literature fall outside the scope of these classes. During our review, we therefore applied an expanded set of indicator classes, as proposed by Czúcz et al. (2021), to identify the use of auxiliary information on pressures, stable environmental characteristics and ecosystem services which, whilst often used as proxies for condition, do not reflect the key characteristics of ecosystems within the context of the ECT. The details of these additional classes, referred to as the 'ECT+' classes, are included in Table A2.

2.2. Selection of relevant literature for review

To ensure transparency and minimise bias in literature selection, we took into account the recommendations of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement (Moher et al., 2009), which provides guidance for the stages of identification, screening and inclusion of relevant items for systematic literature reviews. Fig. 1 details these steps up to retrieval of data from the final selection of studies. To identify relevant items, we first developed a search query to filter a central literature corpus developed within the

European Union Horizon project "Science for Evidence-based and Sustainable Decisions about Natural Capital (SELINA)" (<https://project-selina.eu/>). The SELINA database collated entries from the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) online citation databases on research topics covering ecosystem condition, ecosystem services and ecosystem accounting. As the SELINA project focuses on the most recent developments in these areas to reflect the revision of the SEEA, the literature identified was limited to items published from 2018 to 2022. The full details of the development of this database and the search strategies used are described in Seguin et al. (2025).

We filtered the initial 108,064 publications included in the SELINA database using a search strategy formed of four key terms: i) synonyms of 'ecosystem' (i.e. 'ecosystem', 'ecological', 'habitat', 'environment', 'biological', and the specific ecosystem types according to the MAES typology (Maes et al., 2013)); ii) synonyms of 'condition' (i.e. 'condition', 'quality', 'function', 'state/status', 'health', 'naturalness'); iii) terms indicating 'quantification' (i.e. 'indicator', 'variable', 'assessment'); and iv) terms indicating spatially explicit assessment (i.e. 'spatially explicit', 'map', 'spatial distribution', 'spatial modelling', 'spatial variability', 'spatial relationship'). Full details of the search terms used to filter the database, including the synonyms of 'condition' considered in this work, are included in Supplementary Material. From

Fig. 1. Identification of relevant literature for systematic review, adapted from the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement (adapted from Page et al. (2021), CC BY 4.0).

the resulting 10,224 publications, we excluded 4,369 duplicate records. We excluded an additional 64 records which either referred to retractions, book chapters, and 1,164 studies which were published in journals targeting disciplines such as health science and medicine, mechanical and electrical engineering, and sociology, because of a low probability these papers were related to ecosystem condition. We manually screened the 4,627 remaining publications to exclude those that did not include a map (1,583 publications), as a proxy for use of spatial data. We excluded 127 records for which no full text was available.

We screened the title and abstract of 2,917 publications to determine whether they met the inclusion criterion of being an application of EC indicators. For this stage, we implemented an automated approach using the generative AI model gpt-3.5, the details of which are provided in Nicholson Thomas et al. (2024). This resulted in 853 papers being assessed for eligibility based on the full text, which were randomly assigned to 18 reviewers.

2.3. Data collection and processing

Screening for eligibility and subsequent data collection were carried out using an online questionnaire (a spreadsheet-based version of which is available in [Supplementary Material](#)). Reviewers were first asked to indicate whether the study met the criteria for inclusion in the review based on an assessment of the full text. The criteria for inclusion were as follows:

- Screening criterion 1: The publication is a scientific article written in English and published from 2018 to 2022.
- Screening criterion 2: The publication contains at least one metric that is spatially explicit, based on quantitative data, linked to a specific ecosystem type and used by the authors to characterise the condition of the ecosystem studied.

A further 473 publications were excluded following a negative response to the screening criteria. Upon affirmative answers to both screening questions, reviewers were guided to respond to a series of questions in three sections. The questions collected details of the study and its context, the indicators used to quantify EC, and the datasets used for each indicator. Data for publications covering marine and coastal ecosystems were collected but were analysed separately under the SELINA project due to their extensive coverage under the Marine

Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and distinct management priorities and are therefore excluded from this review.

To ensure consistency and objectivity in the process, the questionnaire template was developed collaboratively with most of the reviewers, and questions were given predefined response options where possible and appropriate. Additionally, reviewers received a guidance manual to clarify potential responses and were offered weekly help sessions during the data collection period to ensure a clear understanding of the review criteria and a high consistency in data collection. Reviewers were encouraged to avoid interpretation of what constitutes an appropriate indicator of EC during the review process beyond the accepted synonyms. For quality control, an initial pilot review was carried out on a sample of publications to identify potential issues and collect feedback to adjust the questionnaire as necessary and correct differences in understanding. Additionally, 2 papers were assigned to 2 reviewers to provide a qualitative estimate of reviewer consistency, helping to identify points where guidance might need to be updated.

Data extracted from the reviewed papers were consolidated into a single database. We performed basic cleaning to standardise terminology and ensure consistency across entries, including the harmonisation of indicator names and dataset categories. We conducted a descriptive analysis of the dataset to explore overall patterns, grouping indicators by thematic category, ecosystem type, and other relevant variables. We summarised the frequency and proportion of indicators across categories and generated plots including a set intersection diagram and categorical flow charts to visualise relationships and distributions. All analyses were conducted using R Statistical Software (v4.2.2; [R Core Team, 2021](#)). Data processing and visualisation were carried out using the *tidyverse* package ([Wickham et al., 2019](#)). Set intersections were visualised using the *UpsetR* ([Conway et al., 2017](#)) and *ComplexHeatmap* ([Gu, 2022](#)) packages, and categorical flows with the *ggsankey* package ([Sjoberg, 2021](#)).

3. Results

3.1. Context and applications of spatially explicit EC indicators

Information was retrieved from 302 papers covering terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems including forests, urban ecosystems, rivers and lakes, agroecosystems, heathlands and/or grasslands, and wetlands. The geographical focus of reviewed literature shows the persistence of gaps, likely reflecting known publication and language biases, with relatively

Fig. 2. Number of reviewed publications per country. Note that 15 continental, EU, and global studies do not appear on the map. Countries not covered in the reviewed publications are shown in grey.

few studies addressing ecosystems in Africa or Central and South America (Fig. 2). In contrast, a disproportionately high number of studies focused on ecosystems in China (number of papers (n_p) = 97), the United States of America (n_p = 38) and India (n_p = 28). A small number of studies covered the European/EU (n_p = 7) or global extent (n_p = 6).

Fig. 3 highlights a corresponding imbalance in the type of ecosystems in which spatially explicit EC indicators have been applied.

Forests were the most frequently studied ecosystem type (n_p = 63; 21 %), followed by rivers and lakes (n_p = 50; 18 %) and urban ecosystems (n_p = 48; 16 %). A substantial number of studies (n_p = 59; 20 %) assessed multiple ecosystems. Wetlands, heathlands and/or grasslands, and agroecosystems were considerably less studied, each addressed in only 16 publications (around 5 % of reviewed literature each). Studies applied indicators across the full range of potential spatial scopes from the patch to global level, but were less likely to apply spatially explicit indicators to a geographic extent at the national (n_p = 28) or broader geographic extents. The primary motivation for using EC indicators was the mapping and assessment of condition directly (n_p = 201). Indicators have been used for the planning or evaluation of conservation and

restoration measures in 87 studies. Some studies also used EC indicators in the mapping or assessment of ES (n_p = 52).

Information for a total of 1,573 individual indicators and 121 composite EC indices were retrieved across all studies. There was a low level of reporting on the reliability of indicator applications with some validation or ground-truthing of indicator values carried out for 21 % of indicators (Fig. 4). Uncertainty of indicator values was considered for only 15 % of indicators, with 9 % of indicators accompanied by a quantitative assessment of uncertainty. A small proportion of studies provided qualitative statements on the uncertainty of indicator values.

Spatially explicit indicators were in most cases presented as values per basic spatial unit (pixel or grid cells) with a tendency towards a spatial resolution less than 500 m (number of indicators (n_i) = 465). In general, studies quantified EC at a single point in time, with 121 publications (n_i = 502) recording values at multiple points in time. The spatial resolution and temporal recurrence of underlying data were, however, in general not specified. In most of the cases where spatial resolution was retrieved during the review, this was in reference to remote sensing data products with a spatial resolution of 10–30 m.

Fig. 3. Ecosystem type and spatial scope covered by reviewed publications. Descriptions of the categories used for spatial scope are included in table A3.

Fig. 4. Responses for a) consideration of uncertainty and, b) validation of indicator values across individual indicators recorded.

Fig. 5. a) coverage of ECT classes across all indicators, b) most frequent intersections of ECT classes in the form of co-occurrence in studies, across all publications (more than 20 observations), c) indicators per publication for forest, urban, and rivers and lakes, coloured by ECT class. each radial line represents a publication.

3.2. Alignment of spatially explicit indicator applications with comprehensive assessment of EC

This review revealed the multiple perspectives from which ecosystem condition is quantified in the scientific literature. Indeed, whilst only 40 studies placed their assessment within the context of a previously published EC conceptual framework, those that did aligned their selection of indicators with a variety of different frameworks, including the Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystem Services (MAES) framework, the Water Framework Directive, and Ecological Integrity metrics. Indicator selection varied significantly by spatial and theoretical context, with high diversity in indicators; based on their names we identified 1,033 unique indicators out of 1,694 total indicators. Only 154 indicators appeared in multiple studies. Most indicators (80 %) were not compared to reference levels or reference conditions, essentially remaining unscaled variables. When reference levels or conditions were used, and sufficiently described for reviewers to classify the approach, the reference was mostly set using an expert-based approach ($n_i = 80$), a simple data-driven approach ($n_i = 50$), or using a natural reference condition ($n_i = 40$).

Our results highlight a prevalence of indicators of structural, physical, and chemical state characteristics, with limited examples of indicators of landscape, and compositional state and functional state characteristics (Fig. 5a). Excluding composite indicators, studies used an average of 5.5 EC indicators (with a range from 1 to 43) but employed a restricted scope in terms of the ecosystem characteristics these indicators represented. Indeed, none of the reviewed literature items addressed all the 6 indicator classes of the ECT (physical, chemical, compositional, structural, and functional state, and landscape characteristics). Instead, where multiple classes of indicators were used to quantify condition, the most common combinations were the use of indicators of structural state with indicators of physical state or stable environmental characteristics such as temperature and precipitation (Fig. 5b). Notable differences in the ecosystem characteristics covered can be observed across the main ecosystem types recorded (Fig. 5c), with a bias towards indicators of structural state applied in forest ecosystems and chemical state in rivers and lakes. Urban ecosystems showed a variety of approaches, with some studies relying on physical or structural state indicators, and others largely based on landscape characteristics.

The use of approaches outside the current framework was

widespread in the literature reviewed, with 583 indicators (37 %) recorded that do not align with the descriptions of the ECT classes (Fig. 6). These metrics primarily quantified stable environmental characteristics ($n_i = 176$) or represented the range of diverse pressures acting on ecosystems ($n_i = 147$) such as land use intensity or the application of pesticides and fertilisers. Studies also used pre-aggregated indicators including soil or water quality indices, or indicators of ecosystem extent and ecosystem services to quantify EC. Indicators falling outside the ECT classes were rarely employed exclusively to describe EC and were generally combined with ECT indicators. For example, Fernandez et al. (2019) used indicators of pressures of road density and landscape development intensity to support metrics of imperviousness and fragmentation of wetlands.

3.3. Main types of data used to operationalise spatially explicit EC indicators

The use of remote sensing data products was prevalent in the studies reviewed, appearing in 172 publications. Satellite imagery, including the use of long-term multispectral imagery from Landsat, Sentinel as well as minor usage of hyperspectral data, was the most frequently applied dataset subtype ($n_i = 357$). In particular, the use of vegetation indices (including Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and various adjusted spectral indices such as Modified Red Edge NDVI and Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)) derived from satellite imagery is widespread across ecosystem types (e.g. Abdollahnejad & Panagiotidis, 2020, Firozjahi et al., 2020, Kayet et al., 2019, Li et al., 2021, Roshani et al., 2023). The use of variables derived from this type of data may include some redundancy, with 66 % of studies using long-term multispectral imagery calculating multiple indicators from the same data source (such as a set of Landsat or Sentinel images). For example, in the study of Chen et al. (2019), in which structural and functional variables of canopy closure, stand density, forest age, stand volume and soil fertility were derived from Landsat imagery to describe EC, it was noted that the spatial variation was primarily driven by a subset of the indicators used to describe functional state characteristics. We found few examples of studies using key continental and global processed datasets, such as various MODIS processed data products and CORINE Land Cover ($n_i = 24$ and 19 respectively) despite their accessibility, high temporal availability and spatio-temporal resolution.

Remote sensing data was used in all ecosystem types to derive

Fig. 6. Distribution of indicators across auxiliary ECT+ classes.

Fig. 7. Sankey diagram showing the data types and subtypes used in developing the different classes of indicators used in EC studies in forest ecosystems.

Fig. 8. Sankey diagram showing the data types and subtypes used in developing the different classes of indicators used in EC studies in river and lake ecosystems.

indicators of all characteristics. However, it was less frequently used to calculate indicators of compositional state characteristics, with the few instances recorded restricted to indicators of tree species composition (e.g. Riedler & Lang, 2018). More frequently, indicators of compositional state relied on the use of direct measurement data interpolated from point locations to produce spatially explicit values as defined by the inclusion criteria (e.g. Pompeu, 2022). In other cases, the calculation of functional metrics required support from complementary data types to provide a comprehensive assessment. For example, Zelený et al. (2020) focused primarily on applying functional indicators, such as net primary productivity and metabolic respiration, derived from satellite imagery to assess EC in the context of agroecosystems and forests. However, their approach required the use of secondary spatial datasets including agricultural census data of harvest values to show functional indicators of biomass production.

The widespread adoption of remote sensing data has significantly advanced the ability to estimate EC in forest ecosystems at high-resolution by leveraging multiple structural variables for assessment (e.g. Riedler & Lang, 2018, Virkkala et al., 2022, López Serrano et al., 2021), as shown in Fig. 7. To a lesser extent, we also observe the use of active remote sensing techniques including radar and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) to derive metrics of forest structural state.

River and lake ecosystems were assessed primarily using chemical state metrics, as these studies tended to equate EC with water quality. These indicators relied heavily on measurement and field data to produce EC estimates at the local and large ecosystem asset scale (Fig. 8). With a focus on water quality, consideration of the landscape characteristics of freshwater ecosystems was more common in publications which also assessed other ecosystem types alongside rivers and lakes (reclassified for the present analysis as ‘various’). Whilst remote sensing data was also applied to estimate many of these water quality indicators, such as the concentration of chlorophyll-a in water, and Secchi depth

(reflecting water clarity), the use of long-term multispectral images was commonly combined with in-situ measurements to strengthen the validity of indicator values (e.g. Markogianni et al., 2022).

Studies of urban ecosystems, however, were more likely to use indicators of landscape characteristics, with publications assuming the urban ecosystem to be a mosaic of green space and other uses (Fig. 9). The use of remote sensing data products was again observed for all types of indicators. However, compared with other ecosystem types, a higher proportion of indicators were based on Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) datasets. For example, Soltanifard & Jafari (2019) assessed the ecological quality of urban green space in Iran using indicators of landscape composition and configuration. For urban ecosystems, we also observed use of socio-economic datasets and indicator values derived from expert opinion.

In studies of agroecosystems, a variety of data types were used to develop indicators primarily of physical state, such as metrics referring to soil structure and erodibility. Studies of wetlands also focused on physical state characteristics, relying mostly on remote sensing data or LULC datasets to develop indicators such as imperviousness. Studies on heathlands and/or grasslands followed the general trends observed in the whole dataset, with remote sensing data frequently used to develop indicators of the most commonly applied ECT classes (see Supplementary Material for Sankey diagrams of these ecosystems).

3.4. Most common EC indicators operationalised in the literature and datasets used for their development

There was a high variety in the unique indicators used across ecosystem types, with only 1 indicator (NDVI) appearing across all ecosystem types surveyed. Fig. 10 summarises the main indicators identified in the literature by ecosystem type, focusing on those used in more than two studies. Amongst agroecosystems, wetlands, and

Fig. 9. Sankey diagram showing the data types and subtypes used in developing the different classes of indicators used in EC studies in urban ecosystems.

Fig. 10. Summary of main indicators (>2 instances) identified in the literature by ecosystem type. The list of all indicators with >1 instance in the reviewed literature is included in Supplementary Material.

heathlands and/or grasslands, the previously stated low coverage in the reviewed literature and high variety of individual indicators applied lead to only one indicator from agroecosystems being included in Fig. 10. In studies on forests, rivers and lakes, and urban ecosystems, long-term multispectral imagery was the dataset subtype most frequently used for repeated indicators, and is employed to derive indicators such as NDVI, above-ground biomass, and chlorophyll-a concentration. This dataset type was often combined with other remote sensing data products, field measurements, and processed Earth Observation data. In forest ecosystems, structural state indicators like NDVI, above-ground biomass, and forest height are prevalent. These indicators are typically derived from long-term multispectral images, LiDAR, and field data. In rivers and lakes, chemical state indicators, such as chlorophyll-a concentration and Secchi depth dominate and were mainly derived from multispectral imagery but in many cases also

incorporated field data. Applications of the main indicators included in Fig. 10 were characterised by the use of fine spatial resolution (<500 m), and incorporate multitemporal assessments to track changes over time. However, those indicators that also use active remote sensing methods, such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and LiDAR, were less likely to have indicator values assessed at multiple points in time within the same study.

Urban ecosystems presented a greater diversity of indicators and dataset types. NDVI, Land Surface Temperature (LST), Wetness (referring to moisture content in both vegetation and soil as derived from spectral reflectance patterns), and Normalised Difference Bare Soil Index (NDBSI) were commonly used, reflecting the inclusion of studies primarily assessing ecosystems in China, in which these spectral indices were applied in the context of ecosystem health assessment using the Remote Sensing Ecological Index (RSEI) (e.g. Shi & Li, 2021, Sun et al.,

2022, Xiong et al., 2022). In terms of datasets, in addition to multi-spectral imagery, there was significant use of socio-economic datasets, LULC maps, and national census data. These datasets were applied to measure pressures, such as population and household density, which are specific to urban environments. In some contexts, LULC data was directly used in the form of the coverage or extent of specific classes (see Land Use/ Land Cover (LULC) in Fig. 10). Despite the prevalence of landscape indicators used in urban settings, the most frequently observed landscape indicator, contagion (reflecting the degree of aggregation of landscape elements), was only applied in 3 different studies of urban ecosystems. This reflects the high variety of individual landscape metrics applied.

4. Discussion

4.1. Implications for standardised monitoring of ecosystem condition

Reconciling data gaps for comprehensive coverage

Our results show that the scientific literature on EC tends not to consider the full range of ecosystem characteristics, with a notably low application of spatially explicit indicators of compositional and functional state characteristics. In contrast, Maes et al. (2020) did not identify such deficits in their review, which focused on national-level assessments and placed less-demanding requirements on the use of spatially explicit data. The absence of similar gaps in their findings suggests that the biases observed in coverage of the ECT classes are likely driven by limitations in data availability and usability rather than a lack of recognition of their instrumental relevance. This points to the relative complexity in defining and measuring meaningful compositional and functional indicators compared to other elements of the ECT. Efforts have been made to collate globally available datasets on biodiversity, but inconsistent update frequencies and gaps in taxonomic and geographical coverage remain a barrier to widespread usage (Stephenson & Stengel, 2020). There is significant potential for these gaps to be filled, for example with developments in process-explicit models which are facilitating increasingly realistic estimation of spatiotemporal species diversity (Pilowsky et al., 2022). In addition to developing reliable datasets that are spatially explicit and encompass diverse ecosystem characteristics, understanding the uptake and validity of these datasets when used should be improved.

Potential of remote sensing for standardised approaches

We find remote sensing, particularly multispectral imagery from Landsat and Sentinel satellite missions, central to EC indicator development due to its accessibility, and scalability and wide applicability of indicators derived from this data across ecosystem types. Drawing inspiration from the concepts used to identify candidate variables for Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) (Pereira et al., 2013, Reddy et al., 2021), remote sensing has the potential to provide a consistently updated data source for monitoring of EC. However, some ecosystem types, such as urban ecosystems, and rivers and lakes, rely more heavily on other data sources, reflecting their unique assessment needs and the diverse ecosystem subtypes they encompass. Our findings highlight the broad usability of remote sensing indicators while underlining the importance of integrating additional datasets for context-specific assessments. While remote sensing offers significant advantages, its limitations, such as potential gaps in fine-scale validation, necessitate complementary field-based measurements. Field data provide critical contextual insights and validation, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of a condition assessment based on remote sensing-derived indicators. Approaches that take into account the benefits of multiple types of data can result in robust, accessible sets of indicators that balance global applicability with local relevance.

Balancing standardisation and context-specificity in indicator selection

The variability in datasets and indicators used across ecosystem assessments prevents the definition of universal minimum indicators. We observed that ecosystem types are assessed differently, with distinct

focuses reflecting the environmental attributes deemed more or less essential for defining a well-functioning ecosystem. This underscores the need for ecosystem-specific sets of indicators while maintaining comparability across studies. While standardisation would aid compatibility, an overly rigid approach risks overlooking critical ecological and contextual nuances and reducing legitimacy of indicators towards stakeholders.

4.2. Limitations

Despite the contributions of our review to understanding of the use of EC indicators, there are several limitations to the approach taken. Firstly, the study aimed to cover a broad understanding of ecosystem condition. However, the variety of contexts in which potentially relevant indicators are used may mean that relevant spatially explicit indicators for ecosystem condition may have been overlooked. In particular, the search strategy was not designed to capture studies focusing on individual ecosystem characteristics without the goal of comprehensive ecosystem assessment. Additionally, the review was limited to published literature, excluding grey literature, and covered a short timeframe. This restricted scope provides only a snapshot of the potential for EC assessment and may not fully reflect the diversity of available approaches. Newly published research rarely focuses on already established monitoring methods, which may lead to the over-representation of certain newer data types (e.g. remote sensing) and the under-representation of some otherwise relevant and widely used data and databases.

Challenges related to indicator evaluation also emerged during our analysis. Our study assumes frequency of use to be representative of the usability and transferability of indicators. However, this does not amount to a full assessment of their relevance for evaluating EC or of factors influencing their application beyond data availability. We also note that, whilst the extension of indicator classification to include the ECT+ classes allows for some indication of whether indicators adhere to describing ecosystem characteristics, the relevance of some indicators deemed important by individual authors could still be questioned. Distinguishing 'individual' indicators adds further complexity, with different approaches observed in the literature, such as treating maximum and minimum values of a metric as multiple or one single indicators. Similarly, distinguishing and classifying individual datasets posed challenges in some reviewed studies, as reflected in the high proportion of datasets categorized as "other". Additionally, many studies utilized subsets of larger datasets, which may have different spatial or temporal coverage, potentially limiting a comprehensive understanding of dataset characteristics.

Furthermore, our ability to analyse temporal scale across studies was constrained. Although we recorded whether assessments covered more than one time step, more detailed information on temporal grain, resolution or frequency of measurement was rarely reported in a consistent format across the studies reviewed. This lack of standardised temporal reporting limited not only the comparability of studies in this regard, but also our capacity to assess how well indicators support the tracking of changes in ecosystem condition over time. As a result, important questions about the sensitivity, responsiveness and relevance over time of EC indicators remain largely unaddressed in our analysis.

4.3. Suggestions for future research

Future research efforts should prioritise the testing and validation of compositional and functional state indicators for describing condition, so as to provide clarity on the barriers to their use in EC assessment. Continued discussion on minimum effective indicator sets could be supported by reducing redundancy among indicators derived from the same datasets and addressing repeated indicator classes within studies, including through the use of statistical methods such as regression, which has been anecdotally noted in the literature. Furthermore, the

complexity of data-to-indicator pipelines warrants further analysis, as methods for deriving indicators from datasets significantly influence the accuracy of spatially explicit outputs. We identified several biases in the published literature on EC, highlighting the need for increased research on the condition of agroecosystems, heathlands and/or grasslands, and wetlands.

The limited comparisons to reference levels, along with the lack of validation and uncertainty analysis, remain key barriers to the applicability of EC indicators and should be prioritized in future research. Furthermore, greater consideration of temporal changes in indicators would significantly enhance the evaluation of ecosystem condition for monitoring and restoration, as such data are crucial for understanding ecosystem dynamics beyond static assessments. Explicit attention to not only the ecological relevance of indicators but also to the availability and continuity of data over time is needed, as these factors affect their suitability for detecting temporal trends and supporting long-term monitoring.

5. Conclusions

Through the systematic review of recent applications of ecosystem condition indicators, we confirm the critical role of spatially explicit data in ecosystem condition assessment, yet show that certain ecological characteristics remain challenging to measure comprehensively. The prevalence of remote sensing products in the reviewed studies indicates their accessibility and scalability for EC assessment and offers potential for implementing consistent monitoring approaches. However, limitations in temporal resolution and ecosystem specificity suggest that supplementary datasets, including field measurements, remain necessary in many contexts for accurate and robust assessment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Isabel Nicholson Thomas: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Filipe Bernardo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Constantin Cazacu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ján Černecký:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Chiara Cortinovis:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Bálint**

Appendix

Table A1

ECT classes (Czúcz et al., 2021).

Code	Class name	Class description	Examples
A1	Physical state characteristics	Physical descriptors of the abiotic components of the ecosystem	Soil structure, water availability
A2	Chemical state characteristics	Chemical composition of abiotic ecosystem compartments	Soil nutrient levels, water quality, air pollutant concentrations
B1	Compositional state characteristics	Composition / diversity of ecological communities at a given location and time	Presence / abundance of key species, diversity of relevant species groups
B2	Structural state characteristics	Aggregate properties (e.g. mass, density) of the whole ecosystem or its main biotic components	Total biomass, canopy coverage, chlorophyll content, annual maximum NDVI
B3	Functional state characteristics	Summary statistics (e.g. frequency, intensity) of the biological, chemical, and physical interactions between the main ecosystem compartments	Primary productivity, community age, disturbance frequency
C1	Landscape characteristics	Metrics describing mosaics of ecosystem types at coarse (landscape, seascape) spatial scales	Landscape diversity, connectivity, fragmentation

Czúcz: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Helena Duchkova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Martina Kičić:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Sabine Lange:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Xavier Lecomte:** Writing – review & editing. **Zhi Yi Vanessa Lim:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Alon Lotan:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ulla Mörtberg:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Chiara Parretta:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Paula Rendón:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Philip Roche:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Eszter Tanács:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Dijana Vuletić:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Christos Zoumides:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Adrienne Grêt-Regamey:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT (<https://chatgpt.com/>) to edit and refine written content. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Anna Porucznik, Jessica Edwards, Jinhao Wang, Ziqi Wang, Har'el Agra, Analena Mill, Isa Wildner, Meri Lappalainen and Viktória Ďuricová for additional support reviewing literature. We thank Ralph Sonderegger for help with visualisations and Orencio Robaina Martinez de Salinas for technical support. This work was funded by the European Union under grant agreement No. 101060415, SELINA (Science for Evidence-Based and Sustainable Decisions About Natural Capital).

Table A2
ECT + classes (Czúcz et al., 2021).

Code	Class name	Class description	Examples
XENV	Stable environmental characteristics	Climatic and other environmental variables which in general change slowly and are largely external to the ecosystems	Climate (precipitation or temperature), slope, aspect, geology
XES	Ecosystem services	Measurable parameters or metrics used to assess and monitor provision or demand of ES.	Specific services or broad categories (cultural services, provisioning services etc)
XEE	Ecosystem extent	The area/cover/share of the main (=MAES) ETs (in the landscape).	Area (specified for ET recorded in B.08, or generic)
XAG	Pre-aggregated indicators	Data collected and processed for various policies are often available in the form of (highly) aggregated indices.	WFD ecological condition index, or the Art17 structure & function parameters. We would also include EC indices such as 'ecosystem health', 'ecosystem condition'
XMA	Natural resource management	Ecosystem management (grazing, felling, fishing, agriculture...) characterized with its intensity. This class may include indicators/densities of the infrastructure for management/extraction (e.g. forest road density...). Indicators for stocks (that are being extracted, e.g. fish, game, timber...) should be considered as B1, B2, or A1 (where it best fits).	Grazing, felling, fishing, agriculture, forest road density
XAC	Accessibility	Accessibility for humans typically for ES "extraction" activities.	Road (or channel) density, human population density, distance from roads or human population centres.
XPA	Protected areas	Indicators highlighting administrative land designations	Status/degree of nature protection
XPR	Pressures	'Raw' pressure indicators given as human extraction/ emission/ immission/ transformation (=change) rates. (The related stocks (e.g. pollutant concentrations, impervious surfaces, hunted species, etc.) should be assigned to its main class (typically A2, A1 or B2, or possibly also B1, XEE)	Pollutant loads/in-flows, habitat loss
B2/ C1	Embedded (sub)types	The abundance of embedded "subgrid" fragments of other ETs in an embedding ET	Hedgerows in an agricultural ET
O	Other	Indicator is clear but does not fit in any of the above classes	
U	Unclear	Indicator name is insufficiently clear for classification	

Table A3
Descriptions of spatial scope/coverage used to classify data.

Title	Description
Global	Metric covers the whole Earth
Continental	Metric covers one or more continents (or more than 10 countries)
National	Metric covers one or more countries
Regional	A large area which could support a diversity of ecosystems linked to an administrative delimitation
Landscape	A large area containing groups of contiguous, interconnected ecosystem assets representing a range of different ecosystem types, not linked to an administrative delimitation.
Large ecosystem asset	Large areas of one ecosystem type/asset (e.g. large forests), not linked to an administrative delimitation.
Local	A small area which can support a diversity of ecosystems, linked to an administrative delimitation
Patch	A small area, smaller or equal to the size of a single small ecosystem asset, not linked to an administrative delimitation

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113952>.

Data availability

Data for this study are available on Zenodo at doi:10.5281/zenodo.15096859

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